

Uzbek national games as speech therapy for children with speech defects

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Abstract

This article provides information on Uzbek national games as speech therapy and their role in the comprehensive development of the individual in speech therapy work for children with speech disabilities. At the same time, the types of the speech therapy games and their characteristics are involved.

Keywords: National games, didactic games, ruled games, action games,

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Introduction:

Our country has always been rich for its own heroes and defenders and cared for them lovingly. Folk games play an important role in the development of children to be physically strong and mature. The national games, which have been around for centuries, have a bright future and a happy life. After all, the physically strong and maturity of generation has always been and will remain one of the main issues in every society, that is, the priorities of the state system.

Material and Methods:

One of the archaic genres of the Uzbek people's culture is the art of play. Games are an ancient but always young art form that has been living and shaping modern Uzbek art for a long time, with its own history and evolving in each period. In ancient Turan, including the ancestors and grandmothers of the Uzbek people, the tribes and clans related to the social life, social aesthetics, ethnic worldview, national characteristics, and various ethnographic content - colorful games in the meanings of people related to lifestyle, conscious play is the first roots of action. As a result, they have a long history of processes, ranging from the most basic, simple elements to complex forms. From birth to the grave, man is engaged in games. So games are an integral part of human life. Each game consists not only of simple actions (physical) or mental situations, but also of a certain rhythm, tone, artistic emotional expression, a certain plot, and compositional complexity. The game also shows the strength, intelligence, ingenuity, and dexterity of the performer.

A large part of the national game, which has gone through a long and difficult stage of development, consists of children's games, including children's games for young and middle-aged people. After all, children, like adults, cannot live without games that have a high content of meaning, that give people a lot of fun, and at the same time test them, and they cannot even grow and develop. In fact, every child is formed, and matured as a person in the midst of a variety of games. It is the national games that inspire and develop children's interest in something. It forms the physical, moral, aesthetic, ethnic upbringing, and gradually develops in the heart of these games. In this sense, national games have been an important and necessary educational tool for centuries as an integral part of folk pedagogy. National games are a constant companion of the children's world and are a constant companion today. Why do kids, even adults, hate games and can't imagine their lives without games? This is due, firstly, to the fact that the game is very interesting and uniquely exciting, secondly, it is extremely emotional, and thirdly, it is aimed at improving the taste, thinking, as well as physical strength, to Fourthly, the perception of the surrounding events has a special effect on the knowledge of the world, spiritual-enlightenment and moral education. Children's games, as well as games in general, are a way to lift the deep national spirit, to captivate the heart, to be very moving and exciting.

There is a wise saying in Uzbek: "Look at children's games look at their growth, you can tell who a child is and what he is interested in from the game he plays." It is important to understand that children's behavior, interests, aspirations, goals, habits, and attitudes can be learned from their play. In any case, it is good that Uzbek children grow up in the midst of national games, which are a constant companion of their grandparents from birth to adulthood! Uzbek national children's games have a wide range of themes and methods of performance. There is no social life, no aspect of human relationships that is not covered by the games. In other words, there should be no sphere of our people's life that has not "moved" to the games and has not found its expression in them. Whether it is the culture of our people

in agriculture, animal husbandry, horticulture, profession and science, philosophical aesthetics, ethics or education, ethics are all the subject of national games. In particular, children's national games are full of spiritual, educational and moral concepts. There are countless Uzbek children's national games dedicated to adults and children of the same age. In any case, the games of our people are innumerable. The children's national games, which have come down to us through repeated experiments in the historical path of our people for thousands of years, have become integral and perfect, depending on the content, logic and direction, they can be divided as followings:

1. Seasonal national children's games: national games played in spring, summer and winter.
2. Ceremonial children's national games: rituals, customs, ceremonies, games played on traditional holidays.
3. National labor-related children's games: "Sowing the crop", "Peeling apricots", "Pomegranate fell", "Plowing the land", "Strawberry festival", "Cow milking", "Horse driving" and others.
4. National games of family and household children: "Guest-guest", "Bride unloading", "Mother-child", "Home furnishing", "Puppet game", "Alla-alla", "Cradle Decoration", "Cradle Belt" and more.
5. National games for physically active children: "Chase", "Wise", "Goose-geese", "Chase the ball", "Rabbit-rabbit", "Deft rabbit", "Ball", "Count", "White Bone", "Run", "Zuv-Zuv", "White Poplar-Blue Poplar", "Donkey Ride", "Think", "Don't Listen", "Reach me", "Climbing", "Capricorn", "Boy", "Swimming", "Jumping away", "Climbing on a rope", "Horse game", "Girl chased", "Targeting", "Fencing", "Fast Jumping Underwater", "Rock Climbing", "Compensation Fighting" and more.
6. National games of logical children: quick sayings, puzzle finding games, counting, saying, questions and answers, inventing, restoring memory, challenges, etc.
7. Children's national games related to animals and natural phenomena.
8. Fun children's national games.
9. Music games.

The division of Uzbek children's national games into such types is relative. After all, some games can be played in the winter and spring, while others can be played all year round. Another characteristic of Uzbek children's national games is that they do not choose age. Each of the Uzbek children's national games is a masterpiece in terms of purpose, meaning, and form. Depending on the content and form of the games, the creative potential, ingenuity, and ingenuity of the peoples who created and performed it, as well as the idea that the thinking can be assessed, the creative work of our people on the basis of national games of Uzbek adults and children, admiring and acknowledging his pedagogical ability, intellect, perception, and human qualities. The Uzbek children's national games are the childhood, adolescence, and youth of our people. Education is a school of morality. In children's national games, as well as in other examples of creativity, the spiritual, enlightenment, moral and ethical views of the people, in particular, the Motherland and patriotism, community, friendship, harmony, labor and diligence, science, profession, wisdom, goodness, courage, bravery, vigilance, entrepreneurship, generosity, hospitality, dignity, honor, decency, politeness, - kindness, patience, dexterity, resourcefulness, thought, time and opportunity appreciation, insight, pride, honor, zeal, justice, strength, language richness and ingenuity, the world of childhood, youth and old age, potential and knowledge, experience, etc. and finds expression in practice. Games are the eternal bells of mental movement, wealth, spiritual awakening, and physical freshness, as well as health education and morality. Folk games, including children's national

games, have grown and deepened and reached us from ancient times to the present day, embodying the way of life, dreams, ideals, spiritual-enlightenment, the aesthetic worldview of the people, unlike other arts, the games reflect the spirit of the people, their psychology, their attitude to the upbringing of the younger generation. It is beautiful, meaningful, educational, and corrective. In the national children's game of each nation, we see the image of our wise people, their Uzbek mentality. It is natural to take a creative approach to these folk games, including children's national games, and to introduce and play them, taking into account the abilities and other talents of the children.

Conclusion:

Speech therapy games is essential for being mental and physical maturity of children, especially for children with mental disabilities. The folk games can be easier and interesting to play for children. Preservation of the national games and promoting them more widely among children is played an immense role in preventing speech disorders.

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